

Studies of Cobalt(II) Ions in Synthetic A-zeolite. Reduction, Reoxidation and Adsorption of Carbon Monoxide

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The cycles of reduction and reoxidation were carried out on four samples of Co Na A-zeolites (degree of exchange from 16.06 to 81%) using hydrogen and oxygen gases respectively as reductant and oxidant. Surface areas (monolayer equivalent areas) of reduced sieves were higher than those of unreduced ones. The reflectance spectra of reduced zeolites were nearly featureless. The methanation reaction was not successful. The ratio of CO : Co on unreduced and reduced zeolites was found to be 0.50. The formation of Co^I ions after reduction process is suggested. In Co_{4.0}A case, the zeolite framework has been shown to be destroyed partially. Co_{1.0}A, Co_{2.0}A and Co_{3.0}A, retained their crystalline structures.

ALTHOUGH hydrocarbon synthesis *via* the reaction of CO and H₂ (Fischer-Tropsch synthesis) on metallic cobalt has been the subject of many investigations, relatively little attention has been paid to the production of Co⁰ loaded zeolite by the reduction of Co^{II} ions in the framework of A-type molecular sieves. Detrekoy and Kallo¹ attempted to reduce Co_{4.0}A-zeolite by hydrogen at 760 torr pressure for 1 h at 573-873 K, and no uptake of hydrogen was observed. They concluded that Co⁰ was not formed. Trifiro and Zatorski² attempted to carry out the methanation reaction on Co A-, Co X- and Co Y-zeolites by adopting two procedures, (i) in which carbon monoxide was introduced before hydrogen, and (ii) in which carbon monoxide was introduced after hydrogen. They also concluded that the cobalt(II)-zeolites were inactive under both the procedures. However, we present in this paper the evidence to suggest that the partial reduction of Co^{II} ions in zeolite-A sieve occurs, in contrast to the above findings.

Experimental

Materials: A series of Co Na A-zeolites (Co_{1.0}A, Co_{2.0}A, Co_{3.0}A and Co_{4.0}A) were prepared by exchange of Co^{II} ions into synthetic Na A-zeolite (Lot No. 4941040757), using cobalt chloride (B.D.H.) solution. Synthetic Na A-zeolite was supplied in the form of powder containing no clay-binders by Union Carbide Corp., U.S.A. The abbreviation, (A) represents (Al_{1.5}Si_{1.5}O_{4.5})¹²⁻ in the zeolite A configuration. The degree of ion-exchange was governed by the concentration of the CoCl₂ solution, contact period, and the temperature of slurry. The

detailed procedures for preparation of Co A-zeolites and their volumetric analysis have been described previously³. The structural integrity of the exchanged Co A-zeolites was examined by X-ray diffraction and physical adsorption.

Apparatus and procedure: The cycles of reduction, reoxidation, adsorption of carbon monoxide and surface area measurements were performed on the Co A-zeolites using pyrex glass standard high vacuum system, the system having a total volume 1340 cm³ and ultimate vacuum 10⁻⁶ torr. Pressure measurement was conducted by a McLeod gauge. Controlled heating was performed by cylindrical electric furnace provided with a variac. Temperature, constant to ±2 K, was measured by a chromal/alumel thermocouple.

The samples of the zeolites were investigated in the form of small pieces of broken pressed discs. For obtaining activated 65 mg of the sample, the accurately weighed sample was first evacuated at room temperature for many hours. The temperature of out-gassing of the partially dehydrated sample was then increased slowly up to 673 K, at which it was evacuated for several hours.

Monolayer equivalent area was determined by a point 'B' method at 77 K, using research krypton (99.97% purity) as adsorbate. Hydrogen (99.99% purity), contained in a pyrex bulb, supplied by the B.O.C. Ltd., was used for reduction of the samples. For reoxidation, air was used; prior to admitting the latter in the vacuum system, it was purified by passing through a liquid nitrogen trap. Carbon monoxide (99.95% purity, B.O.C. Ltd.) adsorption on unreduced and reduced samples was carried out at 273 K.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF REDUCTION, REOXIDATION, SURFACE AREA AND ADSORPTION OF CARBON MONOXIDE ON Co A-ZEOLITES

Zeolite sample	Reduction			Reoxidation			Surface area**			Ratio of CO : Co	
	Temp. K	Period h	%	Temp. K	Period h	%	Unreduced	Reduced	Reoxidised	Unreduced	Reduced
Co _{1.0} A*	778	0.05 16 21 or 68	24.98 29.02 33.85	678	12 or 22	48	9	19	—	0.40	0.48
Co _{2.0} A	778	0.05 0.15 0.20 4 6 or 47	6.26 8.10 9.98 14.46 17.2	678	12 or 22	20.7	570	989	640	0.40	0.45
Co _{3.0} A*	778	0.05 11.05 21.15 22 36 or 40	5.16 5.93 12.07 12.7 18.96	678	12	26.8	558	602	590	0.50	0.50
Co _{4.0} A	778	0.05 18.80 22.25 40 or 42	2.58 8.28 8.68 5.09	678	12	8.8	336	288	288	0.06	0.08

* Co_{1.0}A and Co_{3.0}A were reduced upto 40 and 21%, respectively at 848 K. ** Areas expressed as m² g⁻¹ dehydrated zeolite.

The diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded in the visible-uv range (11500-32500 cm⁻¹) at room temperature (298 K) on a Pye Unicam sp 800 spectrophotometer. A specially constructed vacuum cell was used for taking the spectra of dehydrated, reduced and adsorbed carbon monoxide samples.

Results

A summary of the results is given in Table 1. The reduction of all the Co Na A-zeolite samples was investigated at temperatures from 298 to 773 K for several hours. No uptake of hydrogen was observed at any temperature between 298 and 573 K. The reduction of the samples was first observed at ~773 K. The Table 1 shows the percentage reduction of each sample at 773 K with time, and indicates that the reduction of the samples is both temperature and period dependent. The result also shows the percentages of reoxidation of all the four samples of Co A-zeolites at 673 K. No reasonable reoxidation was observed between 298 and 500 K.

The reduction and reoxidation reactions were followed by uptake of hydrogen and oxygen gases, respectively, measured volumetrically. The amount of hydrogen gas consumed in reduction was assumed to be twice the amount of oxygen required to reoxidize the sieve. The colour of the activated zeolites was pale blue. After the reduction process the colour of Co₁A turned light grey. The colour of reduced Co₂A and Co₃A was grey. The colour of Co₄A after hydrogen treatment became dark grey. The following reactions would be expected to take place during reduction.

The colour of the reoxidised Co₁A was very pale grey, Co₂A and Co₃A turned light grey and Co₄A remained dark grey. For reoxidation the following reaction was assumed.

The 2H⁺ in reaction (3) were from reactions (1) and (2).

Table 1 shows that the surface area of Co₂A and Co₃A have increased and of Co₁A decreased after reduction. The isotherms by point 'B' method for the adsorption of CO at 273 K on unreduced and reduced Co₂A are shown in Fig. 1. Table 1 indicates that the ratio of adsorbed carbon monoxide to cobalt on reduced and unreduced samples except Co₄A, is 0.5 at 273 K. The results show that percentage of reoxidation is greater than percentages of reduction. The reflectance spectra of the sample after undergoing different treatments (dehydrated, dehydrated exposed carbon monoxide, reduced and reduced exposed to carbon

Fig. 1. Isotherms of adsorption of carbon monoxide in activated Co_{2.0}A at 273 K: (O) before reduction and (□) after reduction.

monoxide) are shown by curves 1, 2, 3 and 4 in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Diffuse reflectance spectra of $\text{Co}_{1.0}\text{A}$: (1) dehydrated in vacuum at 623 K for 12 h, (2) dehydrated sample exposed to CO at 298 K for 17 h, (3) treated the dehydrated sample with hydrogen at 749 K for 40 h, (4) hydrogen treated sample exposed to CO at 298 K for 10 h.

Discussion

The following evidences suggest that reduction of cobalt(II) ions in molecular sieve A has occurred.

Uptake of hydrogen :

Hydrogen uptake was used to determine the percentage of reduction of each sample. Table 1 indicates that there was a greater hydrogen uptake in $\text{Co}_{1.0}\text{A}$ -zeolite than $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$, $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$ and $\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{A}$. The percentage of reduction could be increased by raising the temperature above 773 K. It was shown⁴ that Co_1A and $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$ were reduced up to 40 and 21% at 848 K.

Surface area :

The reason for the low surface area of Co_1A , as compared to other zeolites (Table 1), is related to the structure of type A-zeolite^{5,6}. The surface area of Co_1A is only its external area⁶, whereas, the surface area of $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$, $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$ and $\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{A}$ are mainly due to their internal crystalline surface as well as the external one. The higher surface area of $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$ as compared to the other zeolites, is due to completely open windows of 8-rings (free diameter of 8-ring = 4.2 Å) which permit the krypton molecules (diameter = 3.9 Å) entry into the maximum number of alpha-cavities of the dehydrated sample. As the divalent cations localise only in the 6-rings^{7,8} of the dehydrated type A-zeolite, therefore in the cases of $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$ and $\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{A}$, it is suggested that to distribute the positive charge of the cations more uniformly, some of the Na ions are again localised at 8-rings and cause the partial blockage of the openings. This suggestion can be supported from the result of surface area measurement of $\text{Ni}_{0.1}\text{A}$ and $\text{Cu}_{0.1}\text{A}$ which were lower than $\text{Ni}_{0.4}\text{A}$ and $\text{Cu}_{0.6}\text{A}$, respectively⁴. In addition to this, the most likely reason for low surface area of $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$ (81% exchanged) in all cases, is the partial collapse of the structure⁹ during dehydration in vacuum above room temperature.

Table 1 shows the unexpected results that the surface areas of the reduced $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$ and $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$

are higher than those of the unreduced samples. It has been shown^{10,11} that when Ni^{II} ions in X-, Y- and A-zeolites are reduced by hydrogen the metallic particles aggregate on the external zeolite surface forming metal crystals of considerable size. Thus, in these cases we also suggest that Co^{II} ions after reduction migrate to the external surface, as a consequence, the vacated 6-rings are filled by the Na^+ ions which were still partially blocking a few of 8-rings. In this way, the maximum number of 8-rings become completely open and krypton molecules can more easily enter into all the alpha-cavities and now more empty space is available for filling them.

There is no significant increase in surface area of the reduced $\text{Co}_{1.0}\text{A}$ ($10 \text{ Na}^+ + 1 \text{ Co}^{2+}$ per unit cell), probably because the 8-rings remain occupied by Na ions even after reduction. The surface area of reduced $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$ is less than the unreduced sample, this may reflect the increased collapse of the framework structure.

Reflectance spectra :

Reflectance spectra and visual examination of the reduced Co A-zeolites indicate the reduction of Co^{II} ions in the zeolites. Comparison of the spectrum of the reduced $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$ shown by curve 3 in Fig. 2, with the spectrum 1 (activated $\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{A}$), the former being almost featureless. The curve 1 shows distinct splitting of higher energy bands. Klier¹¹ interpreted it as that of the Co^{II} ion trigonally coordinated to oxygen atoms in the 6-ring, $[\text{Co}^{2+}(\text{Ox})_3]$ (Ox refers to oxygen atoms in the 6 rings of the zeolite) and this was subsequently confirmed by X-ray diffraction¹². Thus, the featureless of curve 3 indicates the disappearance of $[\text{Co}^{2+}(\text{Ox})_3]$ complexes due to the reduction of Co^{II} ion to Co^I or Co^0 . In order to determine the nature of the reduced cobalt species in the framework of the zeolite, the following experiments were attempted.

Adsorption of carbon monoxide : The curve 2 (Fig. 2), shows that after adsorption of carbon monoxide the weak band at 18300 cm^{-1} shifted towards higher frequency and emerged as a sharp band at 20150 cm^{-1} . The band at 24200 cm^{-1} has diminished. The bands at 13500 and 16200 cm^{-1} are unaffected. The curves 3 and 4 are nearly the same. Amaro *et al.*¹⁴ has previously reported that when dehydrated $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$ is exposed to 716 torr of dry CO, only a weak carbonyl complex is formed. Moreover, it is well known that CO form complexes with transition metals and it can stabilise the low oxidation states of metal atoms¹⁵, thus the ratio of number of adsorbed CO to Co on the reduced sample should be greater than on the unreduced sample, but the results of Table 1 and the isotherms of Fig. 1, indicate nearly the same ratio, i.e. 0.5 ± 0.05 , except $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{A}$, which shows the absence of Co^0 atoms. The ratio of CO : Co of ~ 0.50 predicts that CO is bridging between two cobalt ions of the two adjacent 6-rings⁹

and forming a complex. The possibility of formation of such a complex is also suggested from the result of the ratio of CO : Co = 0.08 on Co_{4.9}A, as in this case the surface area measurement has shown the partial breakdown of the framework and indicates the absence of many cobalt ions from the adjacent 6-rings of the framework of the zeolite.

Attempted methanation reaction : The methanation reaction was attempted on reduced Co_{3.4}A-zeolite at 500, 573 and 673 K. No activity for CH₄ formation was observed. This also indicates the absence of Co^o atoms in the reduced zeolite. Thus, the formation of Co^I ions is suggested.

The mechanism for the reduction of Co^{II} to Co^I is suggested to be that proposed by Herman *et al.*¹⁶ for Cu^{II} ion in Y-zeolite, *i.e.*

The proton produced may react further with skeletal oxygen (O_x) of the zeolite to form OH group,

The parts of the lattice hydroxyl groups are assumed to be dehydroxylated at experimental temperature of the reaction,

where, Z⁺ represents the oxygen deficient site in the framework of the zeolites.

Table I shows that the percent reoxidation is ~5% higher than the reduction. But the following reasons suggest that reoxidation was irreversible, *i.e.* partially reduced cobalt ions could not occupy their initial sites after reoxidation.

(i) **Colours :** As mentioned above the colour of the dehydrated samples of unreduced Co A-zeolites was pale blue due to the formation of trigonal complexes, *i.e.* [Co²⁺(O_x)₃], but the colour of the partially reduced samples of Co A-zeolites after treatment with oxygen did not change from grey to pale blue. This suggests that in the reoxidised Co A-zeolite samples the cobalt ions could not reform their initial trigonal complexes with oxygen atoms of the 6-rings.

(ii) **Surface area :** The samples show that the surface area after reoxidation did not return to their initial values, which are less than reduced samples, but higher than unreduced ones. Jacobs *et al.*¹⁷ investigated the redox behaviour of copper(II) Y-zeolites. They showed that reduction under more severe conditions results in the

formation of copper agglomerates and crystallites. They found that agglomerates are reoxidized reversibly, whilst the crystallites are transformed into CuO, present as an external phase. In conformity with these reports, it can be speculated that the consumption of greater amount of oxygen in the present case might be due to the oxidation of some Co^{II} ions to Co^{III} ions and the resultant formation of oxides, such as Co₂O₃, as well as CoO is proposed.

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